

Literature & case study review on outcomes in payments for ecosystem services / compensation for ecosystem services (PES/CES) programmes

Notes to justice codes

<i>Problematization</i>		1	2	3
DistJ	How is responsibility for environmental problems distributed among stakeholders?	Responsibility primarily placed with marginalized groups and/or upstream landholders (without associated empowerment)	Some responsibility distributed among stakeholders	Definition of problem/solution takes into account indirect drivers, equity/justice considerations, and power relations
Proj	Who is empowered to define environmental problems and solutions?	Problem/solution defined principally by powerful stakeholders	Pushback or eventual partial redefinition by diverse stakeholders	Collaborative/inclusive definition of problem and solution
RecJ	Whose rights, values, worldviews, and knowledge are recognized?	Problem/solution further marginalizes or fails to recognize marginalized rights and values	Some effort to recognize or affirm rights and values with regard to land management in defining problems and solutions	Definition of problem and solution enhance recognition of marginalized values/values of marginalized
SEJ	How are traditional practices and relational values positioned with regard to problem and solution?	Traditional practices problematized or ignored entirely	Neutral or minimal impact, or some effort to accommodate traditional practices and relational values	Problem def and solution support/enhance traditional practices and relational values
<i>Design</i>		1	2	3
DistJ	How are costs and benefits of the program distributed at the design stage?	Costs/benefits inequitably distributed; undue burden on most marginalized; and/or exacerbates inequities	Some effort to address equity in dist of costs/benefits	Program explicitly incorporates equity considerations
Proj	Who is empowered in program design? What is the role of	Top-down design with little participation	Nominal/shallow participation; may be geared mainly to obtaining	Marginalized stakeholders substantively

	marginalized stakeholders?		consent/satisfying safeguard requirements; may be inappropriate to institutional context	empowered in decision-making about program design
RecJ	Does program design recognize/represent marginalized stakeholders' rights, values, and knowledge systems?	No recognition or representation of marginalized stakeholders' rights/values/knowledge	Some nominal recognition of values/knowledge, possibly as 'cultural difference'; may serve to reinforce rather than transform power hierarchies.	Marginalized stakeholders recognized and empowered as equal-status participants; able to represent own values/knowledge; empowerment 'scales up' to have implications beyond program level
SEJ	How does program design address traditional practices and relational values?	Curtailement or criminalization of traditional values and further marginalization of assoc relational values	Some effort at engagement with/mitigating negative effects on traditional practices and relational values	Interventions are designed to support or enhance traditional practices or relational values
Implementation		1	2	3
DistJ	How are costs and benefits of the program actually distributed during implementation?	Costs/benefits inequitably distributed; undue burden on most marginalized; and/or exacerbates inequities; promised benefits do not materialize	Some effort to address equity in dist of costs/benefits; and/or changes to program over time to better incorporate these goals	Dist enhances equity
ProJ	Who is empowered in program implementation? What is the role of marginalized stakeholders?	Virtually no participation in decision-making or monitoring; minimal consultation	Nominal/shallow participation; may be geared mainly to obtaining consent/satisfying safeguard requirements; may be inappropriate to institutional context; participatory monitoring	Marginalized stakeholders substantively empowered in decision-making about program implementation; able to influence change over time; participatory monitoring and enforcement; consistency with institutional context
RecJ	Does program implementation recognize/represent marginalized	No recognition or representation of marginalized	Implementation/targeting involves consultation with local authorities/landowners;	Implementation recognizes/affirms traditional territory, knowledge, and

	stakeholders' rights, values, and knowledge systems?	stakeholders' rights/values/knowledge	Some nominal recognition of values/knowledge; may serve to reinforce rather than transform power hierarchies.	control; Marginalized stakeholders recognized and empowered as equal-status participants in decision-making around implementation; able to represent own values/knowledge
SEJ	How does implementation affect traditional practices and relational values?	Further marginalization, curtailment, or criminalization of traditional practices; further marginalization of relational values	Some efforts to mitigate/adapt program design to redress negative impacts; successful intervention by stakeholders to adapt or subvert program	Implementation supports or enhances traditional practices and relational values